

IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS FIN THE TEACHING OF SCIENCETHE IMPORTANCE OF APPLYING MODERN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES**Jalilova S.**

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ABSTRACT

Since physical science, which has a special role in the development of world culture, plays a leading role in the formation of a new outlook, its teaching in secondary schools remains relevant today. At the same time, the indispensable role of physical science in the search for new energy sources, the study of space, human health, environmental protection, and learning the basics of new technologies should be properly promoted among young people, and its teaching should become the interest of the general public and the state. From this point of view, the purposeful formulation of the content of the school physics course is of particular importance, its formulation is very complex in itself and an important field that serves the interests of the economic development of the state. As we know, every new day the world is becoming more modern, science and technology are developing. In this regard, changes are also taking place in the educational process, and the latest methods tested in practice are used. In recent years, the biggest change in the educational process has been the transition from traditional learning to active learning. For this purpose, all teaching materials have been changed in turn. The modern method is focused on students' activity, independence, and improvement of application skills. Innovative technologies are a way of implementing educational content, a system of forms, methods and means of teaching that ensure the most efficient achievement of the set goals. The choice of teaching technologies is related to the characteristics of the content of the training, the level of development and preparation of students, the number of students, and the level of equipment of the educational process. The article discusses research issues on the effective use of computer technologies and modern information and communication technologies in the education system. Adapting the education system to world standards is one of the important tasks of modern education reforms. A characteristic feature of modern education is the informatization of education and training, taking into account the needs of the information society. In the process of writing the article, the analysis and synthesis of the pedagogical and scientific methodical literature on the research field was carried out, the theoretical analysis of the scientific literature on the problem was carried out, and at the same time, the scientific and scientific-methodological works of scientists-methodologists working in the field of physics teaching methodology and various related articles, documents and materials were examined.

Keywords: innovative technologies, teaching of physics, methodology.

Introduction

Today, the main task of the education system is to help students grow up strong, patriotic, who rely on knowledge and talent, acquire knowledge independently, using modern ICT. It is about raising a healthy, well-rounded and healthy person. Today, innovative pedagogical processes are becoming one of the important components of the education system. After all, innovative pedagogical processes lay the foundation not only for the competitiveness of any educational services market, but also for the intensive development of teacher and student personality, the democratization of interaction and communication between teacher and student, and the development of education. humanization of the educational process, directing students to active learning and self-education, modernization of educational technologies, including the material and technical base of education, the professionalism of teachers, and their creative potential determine the development directions of education. their searches play an important role in the formation of students as personalities. The first is a software product that provides the user with interactivity, that is, a dialogue environment that allows the exchange of commands and responses

between a person and a computer. Second, the environment in which various video and audio effects are used. This is reminiscent of a video that allows the viewer to choose this or that application himself. In addition, multimedia technologies allow the user to design and create static (stationary) and dynamic (moving) images, as well as to broadcast the results of their creation to the external environment through communication channels. The rapid development of multimedia systems was related to the expansion of the capabilities of personal computers and the development of hardware and software. In recent years, computer speed and storage capacity have increased dramatically, as well as expanded graphics capabilities and improved specifications of external storage devices. The development of innovative technologies was greatly helped by the development of video technology, laser discs, as well as sound recording equipment, sound and image production technologies. It was also important to create ways to quickly and efficiently change information for compact (dense) storage and storage of information in memory.

Use of pedagogical techniques in the process of teaching physics

The main strategic direction of the development of the education system consists in solving the problem of student-centered education, where the student's personality will be the focus of the teacher's attention. In such training conditions

The teacher, being a competent consultant and assistant, acts as an organizer of active cognitive activity of students.

If the teacher is actively teaching and the student is not participating in the learning process, you cannot count on success. The teacher should model the content of the academic subject for the entire educational period, set goals, select the most important theoretical information, ensure the use of didactic training tools, predict training results and think about ways to achieve them. The learning process becomes more effective when it is skillfully managed by the teacher.

One of these development directions of the education system is the modular training technology that ensures the student's participation in the educational process, the clarity and specific direction of his actions, the efficiency of mastering the educational material, his cognitive activity, and self-development - control and correction of its activity on this basis.

The developed approaches to the organization of physics teaching are based on the use of pedagogical techniques:(4)

- block-by-block planning of educational material;
- a unified scheme for reviewing the theoretical foundations of the subject;

- use of educational materials and summary tables;
- use of open control materials;
- selection of two types of control (colloquium and test);

- students' open access to reference literature both during class and during oral and written inquiries;
- to take into account the psychophysiological characteristics of the individual.(5)

The purpose of using module technology is to increase students' interest in learning the subject, to increase the quality of knowledge and the efficiency of the educational process, as well as to develop independence in the performance of tasks.

Tasks that help achieve this goal:

- choose educational material (in accordance with the educational program) and presentation methods that allow to develop the creative level of the material;
- to bring the content of the training sessions as close as possible to the interests and needs of the individual;
- to use methods and techniques, pedagogical techniques and tools that help the free development of students' creative potential;
- develop a phased system of knowledge and skills monitoring;
- to make adjustments to students' knowledge and skills.

The principle of modularity, which consists of dividing the teaching material of a subject into modules - certain doses, didactic units (DU), creates conditions for training to be directed to the final result with concrete, well-defined goals, tasks and control forms.

Table 1

Material Didactic Means in the Educational Process

N	Name of the module (didactic units of discipline)	Name of the task topic
1.	Physical foundations of classical mechanics.	1.1. Kinematics and dynamics of a material point.
		1.2. Rigid body as a system of particles. Dynamics of rigid bodies.
		1.3. Work, energy, power.
		1.4. Conservation laws in mechanics.
2	Molecular physics and thermodynamics.	2.1. Thermodynamic systems. Ideal gas. Gas laws. Mendeleev-Clapeyron equation.
		2.2. Physical foundations of molecular kinetic theory. Basic equation of MKT. Average kinetic energy of translational motion molecules of an ideal gas.
		2.3. Fundamentals of thermodynamics. Internal energy. Heat. Methods of heat transfer.
		The first law of thermodynamics and its application to various isoprocesses.
3.	Electricity and magnetism.	3.1. Direct Electric Current. Ohm's Laws and Joule-Lenz Rules Kirchhoff.
		3.2. Magnetic field in vacuum. Magnetic interaction currents. Ampere's law. Lorentz force.
		3.3. Magnetic field of direct currents. Magnetic field strength. Biot-Savart-Laplace law. Magnetic flux.
		The phenomenon of electromagnetic induction. Self-induction
4	Oscillations and waves.	4.1. Mechanical vibrations. Harmonic vibrations. Basic characteristics of oscillatory motion. Pendulums.
		4.2. Waves. Formation of waves. Longitudinal and transverse waves. Wave equation. Plane electromagnetic wave.

5	Optics.	5.1.	Laws of geometric optics.
		5.2.	Elements of the wave theory of light. Interference of light.
			Diffraction of light. Diffraction of light from a single slit. Diffraction grating.
5.3.	Quantum nature of radiation. Photoelectric effect.		
6	Atom, nucleus.	6.1.	The structure of the atom. Bohr's postulates.
		6.2.	Structure and properties of atomic nuclei. Protons and neutrons. Isotopes. Radioactivity. Nuclear reactions.

Thus, the use of block-module learning technology and the rating system for monitoring knowledge in teaching physics allows to stimulate students to perform types of educational activities and affects their learning success. In the process of using the rating system, competition develops among students and interest in science increases, which allows them to reveal their abilities more fully.

In teaching physics Wide application of modern information and communication technologies in education affects the following factors:

- Informatization of science;
- Intellectualization of educational activity;
- Deepening of integration processes;
- Improving the infrastructure of the education system and its management mechanisms.
- Effective organization of pedagogical teaching processes based on modern information technologies:
 - The computer acts as a "manager" and displays on the monitor the results of didactic tasks, test questions, answers to problematic situations, i.e. level of assimilation;
 - it acts as a tool to control the activity of students in the lesson, and the number of completed tasks increases dramatically, as a result, the amount of acquired knowledge increases;
 - Modification of the training structure, ie. implementation of most of the organizational work performed by the teacher with the help of computer technology reduces the problem of lack of time;
 - The student becomes an active participant, expands opportunities for independent learning and becomes a partner who can communicate with the teacher freely and on equal terms.(7)

Multimedia technologies used in the educational process and their types

Multimedia technology (multi-multi, media environment) allows to use several methods of simultaneous presentation of information. These include text, graphics, animation, video and audio. The most important feature of multimedia technologies is interactivity, the ability of the user, the reader, to establish a high level of interaction with working in the information environment.

Multimedia is a combination of several means to present information in one system. As a rule, multimedia is a set of tools for presenting information such as text, sound, graphics, animation, video, spatial modeling in a computer system. The combination of such tools provides a new qualitative level of information acquisition: a person is not only passively obsessive, but also actively involved.(6)

Programs that work with multimedia programs are multimodal, that is, they attract the attention and attention of the audience because they affect several senses at the same time. The content of the multimedia application is carefully thought out by the author when preparing the scenario and is specified when the technological scenario is being drawn up. If the traditional form of presentation of educational information - text and static graphics - has a long history, the experience of using multimedia is measured in years.

Possibilities of using multimedia technologies. The model of illumination of educational materials at the initial stage of design using multimedia technologies allows:

- Clear determination of the content of the material: determination of lecture, practical, laboratory, independent, test tasks;
- present content, slides, presentations created in various animation programs in a visual, understandable and transparent form;
- Determine the content of the multimedia program components: determine what content is presented in the form of animation, video, text, graphics, etc.

Taking into account the achievements of psychology in the development of methods of information visualization on a computer screen allows us to formulate a number of general recommendations. They are:

- ❖ the information displayed on the screen is entered into the system;
- ❖ periodic exchange of visual information for audio information;
- ❖ periodic changes in brightness and color volume;
- ❖ The content of the visualized material should not be too simple or too complex.(2)

A well-designed multimedia program with animation elements, tables and diagrams, accessible animation elements and audio facilitates the work, the comprehension of the studied material helps to understand and remember it, increases the student's activity in learning subjects, provides a clearer and more complete understanding of the studied material (5).

The importance of using multimedia programs created by experienced educators in educational institutions is as follows:

- educational information is fully reflected on the screen using modern multimedia tools;
- it is possible to control knowledge interactively; ^ may be used by more than one student at a time. ^ rational use of time, that is, it becomes possible for students to absorb a large amount of educational information in less time.

➤ students can absorb learning information by repeating it more than once, etc.

Innovative technologies as a means of increasing the efficiency of physics education.

Today, multimedia-based programs are being created in almost every subject, which proves to be more effective in the learning process than traditional teaching materials.

The set of tools that make up multimedia technology provides a new level of quality in the extraction of information that students master, when the student is not passively interested in it, but actively participates. (5)

Multimedia electronic educational resources are created on the basis of multimedia technologies, and researchers have expressed their opinion about the efficiency of their use [5].

Multimedia is a complex type of delivery of educational materials to students based on audio, video, text, graphics and animation effects based on computer software and hardware. Multimedia is the ability to work with various forms of information on a computer: color graphics, dynamic effects in text and graphics, sound output and synthesized music, animation, as well as full-length video clips and videos. Multimedia is a modern computer information technology that allows combining text, sound, video, graphics and animation in a single computer system. Multimedia experience at work - a software-technical environment that represents the input, processing, storage, transfer of information to a computer and the transmission of text, images, video, sound and speech in a necessary and convenient form. The first is a software product that provides the user with interactivity, that is, a dialogue environment that allows the exchange of commands and responses between a person and a computer. Second, the environment in which various video and audio effects are used. This is reminiscent of a video that allows the viewer to choose this or that application himself.

A multimedia product can play music, video clips, animations, photo and slide galleries, various databases, etc. is an interactive computer product included.

Multimedia technology can transmit information in a combination of many forms (including speech, images, drawings, pictures, music, numbers, and letters) that people can simultaneously understand. This technology allows you to search, copy and transfer data to any other computer in a specified format and create any combination of them.

A practical example

The type and appearance of interactive methods are increasing and changing day by day. The ability of a creative teacher to use these methods effectively in the classroom determines the bright future of physics education. The following is an incomplete list of these interactive methods: - "cluster", "mental attack", "intellectual attack", "decision tree", "black box", "scarab", "fish skeleton", "elegant saw", "round snow game", "ice breaker", "lilac flower", "round table", "BxBxB", "Venn diagram", "smart", "zig-zag" strategy, "insert" strategy, "why?", "How?" hierarchical models, etc. (5).

The introduction of new pedagogical technologies in the educational process is one of the modern requirements, which requires pedagogical staff and teachers to constantly work on themselves. As in other disciplines, the use of new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of physics gives good results. The hours allotted to physics are 68 hours in grades 6-9, and 40 hours per semester in vocational colleges (VC) and academic lyceums (AL) (in the field of social sciences and humanities), with 160 hours for the entire course. During these hours, the teacher should be able to give lectures on the course, as well as problem-solving and laboratory classes. Given the fact that college entrance exam questions require you to solve problems primarily in physics, it becomes clear how important it is to solve problems. Students usually solve a maximum of 8, 10 problems in a traditional two-hour class. In this case, the most active students solve the problem quickly, and other slow-moving students remain "empty" until the problem is solved. Poor learners, on the other hand, are often overlooked by the teacher as a "save" without understanding the nature of the problem. The use of interactive methods - new pedagogical technologies - in such lessons gives significant results. One such method is the 6x6 or 6x5 method. When using this method, the lesson process is as follows:

Step 1. Before the lesson, the teacher places 6 chairs around 5 tables. Step 2. Students are divided into 5 groups by the teacher. The teacher can use the following method to divide students into groups: Place a plate with a picture of a specific object (eg, rainbow, crystal, car, northern light, and transistor) on each of the 5 tables (Figure 1). The teacher has a total of 30 leaflets with six images of a transistor, a car, a northern light, a crystal and a rainbow, students take turns choosing one of these colored sheets and taking a seat on the table with the picture. Each team chooses a leader.

Figure 1. Place a plate with a picture of a specific object (eg, rainbow, crystal, car, northern light, and transistor) on each of the 5 tables

Using this method, each participant will act as a participant, listener, and speaker for a short period of time. The use of the "6x5" method in the educational process requires a teacher to be very active, to have pedagogical skills. In this case, it is necessary to form teacher groups in such a way that in each group the active and slow learners are properly distributed. When groups are formed incorrectly, students may waste time without solving the problem [3.94-96]. As physics progresses to higher education, the phenomena and laws become more complex, and the volume of course material increases.

The result

At present, stimulating tools and electronic textbooks are widely used in education. Test systems are used to test and evaluate students' practical and theoretical knowledge through special programs. The internet portal for distance education consists of special websites (Internet resources). The main task of these sites is to organize the educational process or to create an online electronic connection between the student and the teacher, to place teaching materials for teachers on the site, to enable those students to work with information and to use other distance education services. Multimedia is a set of hardware and software that allows a person to communicate with a computer using various natural media: sound, video, graphics, text, animation, etc.

As physics progresses to higher education, the phenomena and laws become more complex, and the volume of course material increases. In conclusion, the following recommendations were made:

The purpose of new pedagogical technologies used in physics education is to bring the student to the learning process center, to develop students' independent and creative activity, to make them active participants in the lesson;

The new pedagogical technologies introduction in physics education as a full-fledged technological process, the educational process technologicalization is a

complex process that requires a strong material and technical base of the educational institution, a lot of time and effort. In order to apply new pedagogical technologies in physics education, the teacher must have high pedagogical skills and take into account the subject of the lesson, the number of students, their interests and abilities.

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